

Table 3

Descriptive statistics of the variables according to teachers, students and exam models, and Kruskal Wallis bilateral asymptotic significance index.

		Kruskal-Wallis Asymptotic sig. (bilateral test)	Model evaluation	N	Missing	Mean	Median	SD	Min.	Max
I_1	Teacher	0,162	A	3 2	4	3.41	4.00	0.837	2	4
			C	1 7	2	3.76	4	0.437	3	4
			B	1 7	0	3.71	4	0.849	1	4
	Student	0,100	A	6 7	8	2.79	3	0.930	1	4
			C	1 6	1	2.75	3	0.951	1	4
			B	7 4	1	3.01	3.00	0.914	1	4
I_2	Teacher		A	3 2	4	2.22	2.00	1.128	1	4
			C	1 6	3	1.31	1.00	0.793	1	4
			B	1 6	1	1.00	1.00	0.000	1	1
	Student		A	6 0	15	1.62	1.00	0.885	1	4
			C	1 5	9	1.45	1	0.794	1	4
			B	3 7	5	1.61	1.00	0.921	1	4
I_3	Teacher	0,000	A	3 2	4	2.72	2.50	1.143	1	4
			C	1 7	2	3.88	4	0.332	3	4
			B	1 6	1	3.88	4.00	0.342	3	4
	Student	0,001	A	6 5	10	3.25	4	0.952	1	4
			C	1 5	6	3.71	4.00	0.559	1	4
			B	6 7	1	3.49	4.00	0.745	1	4
I_4	Teacher	0,000	A	3 2	4	2.75	2.50	0.984	1	4
			C	1 7	2	3.82	4	0.529	2	4
			B	1 6	1	3.94	4.00	0.250	3	4
	Student	0,000	A	6 5	10	3.15	4	1.049	1	4

I_5	Teacher	0,000	C	1 5	7	3.75	4	0.539	1	4
			B	7 4	1	3.58	4.00	0.740	1	4
			A	3 2	4	2.72	3.00	0.888	1	4
	Student	0,002	C	1 7	2	3.53	4	0.624	2	4
			B	1 6	1	3.88	4.00	0.342	3	4
			A	6 4	11	3.22	4.00	0.967	1	4
I_6	Teacher	0,000	C	1 5	9	3.65	4	0.702	1	4
			B	3 7 4	1	3.54	4.00	0.706	1	4
			A	3 2	4	2.53	2.00	1.047	1	4
	Student	0,000	C	1 7	2	3.41	4	0.712	2	4
			B	1 6	1	3.81	4.00	0.403	3	4
			A	6 2	13	2.95	3.00	1.031	1	4
I_7	Teacher	0,000	C	1 5	8	3.59	4.00	0.692	1	4
			B	4 7 3	2	3.38	4	0.793	1	4
			A	3 2	4	2.50	2.00	1.191	1	4
	Student	0,000	C	1 7	2	3.94	4	0.243	3	4
			B	1 6	1	3.81	4.00	0.403	3	4
			A	6 2	13	3.00	3.00	1.116	1	4
I_8	Teacher	0,000	C	1 5	7	3.79	4	0.497	1	4
			B	5 7 2	3	3.57	4.00	0.728	1	4
			A	3 2	4	2.53	2.00	1.016	1	4
	Student	0,000	C	1 6	3	3.56	4.00	0.512	3	4
			B	1 6	1	3.88	4.00	0.342	3	4
			A	6 3	12	2.95	3	0.974	1	4
			C	1 5	8	3.58	4.00	0.703	1	4
			B	4 7 4	1	3.42	4.00	0.811	1	4

I_9	Teacher	0,956	A	3 1	5	2.45	3	1.179	1	4
			C	1 7	2	2.35	2	1.169	1	4
			B	1 6	1	2.44	2.00	1.031	1	4
	Student	0,003	A	6 0	15	1.87	2.00	0.911	1	4
			C	5 6	6	1.50	1.00	0.823	1	4
			B	6 7	8	1.55	1	0.942	1	4
Total_ mean	Teacher		A	3 2	4	2.71	2.38	0.799	1.57	4.00
			C	1 7	2	3.57	3.63	0.283	2.88	4.00
			B	1 7	0	3.70	3.75	0.234	3.25	4.00
	Student		A	6 7	8	3.05	3.25	0.760	1.25	4.00
			C	1 1	1	3.53	3.63	0.438	1.00	4.00
			B	7 4	1	3.43	3.54	0.537	1.38	4.00
